

EXPRESSION OF SEMANTIC RELATIONS OF CAUSE AND EFFECT IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract. This article is written on the topic of expressing the semantic relations of cause and effect in Uzbek and English and their difference, as well as examples. The article used the literature of a number of great writers and scientists.

Keywords: causative, adverbial turnover, postpositive, dynamics, nuance, conjunction.

Introduction

To express a predominantly causal relationship in scientific and journalistic speech, conjunctions are used, such as *due to the fact that*. To express a shade of a weakened causal connection, a conjunction *due to the fact that* is used in book speech. On the contrary, in cases where it is necessary to indicate that the reason given in the subordinate clause is distinguished from other possible reasons or is given as an additional argument, a complex conjunction, *all the more so*, is used. Occasionally there are obsolete causal conjunctions *then what, for*.

Causal clauses are placed both after the main clause and before it. The subordinate clauses are always put in second place, which are associated with the main through conjunctions *because, since, then what, especially since, moreover*, the conjunction *because of* can be used in dismembered form; the conjunction *then that* currently found only in poetic speech (and usually introducing a shade of bookishness), is used both in its entirety and in its dismembered (on the part of intonation) form, however, its constituent element *then* always takes its place at the end of the main sentence. The subordinate clauses, which are connected with the main clause through other conjunctions, are placed before the main clause in those cases when it is necessary to emphasize the reason or basis for something and then indicate the consequence that follows from them. Conjunction *since* at the beginning of the main sentence the particle *that* can correspond.

The subordinate clauses of the consequence are understood as subordinate clauses, in which a fact is stated that is a consequence of an action, or the result of a quality referred to in the main clause. The subordinate clauses of the consequence always take place after the main clause.

Compound sentences with subordinate corollaries are divided into two types, differing both in the nature of the relationship between the simple sentences that make up them, and in the syntactic structure. The subordinate clause of the consequence may contain a message about the result of the action referred to in the main clause, and refer to the main sentence as a whole or to a part of it, which is a participial or adverbial turnover. The subordinate clause in such cases is associated with the main clause with the help of the conjunction *so*.

In direct motivation sentences, the parts are linked as cause and effect. Relationships of direct motivation are expressed by the conjunction *and then*. They are close to relations expressed in sentences with conjunctions *because, since* with a postpositive clause. The difference lies in the fact that in sentences with conjunctions *because, since* motivation relations are not accompanied by expressive layers, but in sentences with conjunction *and then*, these

relations are accompanied by an indication that the phenomenon opposite to that named in the main part would be in conflict with a phenomenon named in the subordinate clause. By the nature of the modal-temporal plan of the subordinate part, conditional sentences are divided into sentences of unreal, potential and real conditions.

In English, in view of its analytical structure, the system of analytical causatives is especially developed, served by a whole series of auxiliary causative verbs. This indicates that in English grammar the expression of causation has acquired a categorical meaning. Without understanding the features of the existence of these connections from the point of view of logic, it is impossible to deeply comprehend them in a sentence as the main unit of syntax.

Due to the fact that in modern English there is no special morphemic expressor of causation, the dependence of lexical units on the syntactic environment is great, i.e. words can receive their full characteristics, as causative and non-causative, under conditions of syntactic compatibility. In other words, the acquisition of causative meaning by non-causative verbs depends on their syntactic environment. The transfer of the category of causation with the help of derivative words formed affixally is not a common way, since individual English affixes, forming words, can simultaneously add shades or additional meanings of causation to the main lexical meaning of the word.

The transfer of causation using units of the syntactic level is the main way in modern English.

The implementation of the means of expressing causality in both languages is carried out in the same way: in journalistic texts, the total number of uses of prepositions and conjunctions is 42.7%, complex sentences - 50.1%, second participial phrases - 1.3% and asyndetic constructions - 5.9%.

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